

Speculation on Kinetic Energy in Quantum Bound States

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. July 16, 2022

Newton's second law $dp/dt = F(x) = -dV/dx$ may be written in terms of x alone i.e. $dp/dx v(x) = -dV/dx$ or $1/(2m) d/dx p^2 = -dV/dx$ leading to the idea of kinetic energy $p^2/2m$ and potential energy $V(x)$.

In (1) we argued that there is velocity, rest mass m_0 , and momentum in quantum mechanics. A free particle, however, does not undergo smooth acceleration as in classical mechanics, and we argued there exists a momentum space wave $\exp(ipx)$ accompanying the moving particle. In such a scenario, force is considered to be probabilistic momentum hits of the form $V_k \exp(ikx)$ leading to a free particle momentum distribution $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. Both of these expressions involve interference due to momentum waves which do not track a particle in time. A mass flux mv or energy flux $p=Ev$ relativistically seems to be the main consideration.

Nevertheless, summing $V_k \exp(ikx)$ over k to obtain $V(x)$ yields a function varying in x alone. This is a kind of average based on interference and $\sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ is an average linked to momentum hits. We speculate that average momentum hits i.e. $-d/dx V(x)$ are linked to momentum flux changes. In other words, even though an impulse is based on p and does not distinguish v i.e. $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$, momentum flux is velocity dependent and appears for an average momentum hit i.e. $-dV/dx$. In such a case $(p_{ave} + dp_{ave})(v_{ave} + dv_{ave}) = 2 p_{ave} dv_{ave}$. This expression, however, contains both forward and backward motion which is part of quantum mechanics. Moving to an average picture seems to introduce time and direction i.e. one uses $p_{ave} dv_{ave}$. This is already a change from a quantum to a classical scenario albeit for averages (which have not been specifically defined). Thus we consider $p_{ave} dv_{ave}$. If this is the case, then: $d/dx p_{ave} 1/m \text{ space} = -dV/dx$ or $1/(2m) p_{ave} p_{ave} = -d/dx V(x)$.

Instead of treating $p_{ave} p_{ave}$ as two separate averages one considers $p_{ave} = p_{rms}$ or $p_{ave} p_{ave} = \langle p^2 \rangle$. Thus the quantum bound picture (at any energy level) becomes a classical type of scenario which includes time and velocity. Note that for a two slit interference pattern, one does not need velocity and time because the interaction with the potentials from both slits is based on $\exp(ipx)$. One does not even need the form of the potential. Interference is the same for $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$ (even though the process takes place during different time intervals, the pattern is not affected). In other words, we argue that Newton's second law might follow from a picture of momentum hits in which a flux i.e. $p=mv$ is treated as a quantity which in an average scenario leads to a second flux i.e. an average momentum flux which reintroduces direction, time and velocity.. This is somewhat like a hydrodynamics scenario.

Momentum wave $\exp(ipx)$ and Interactions

A free classical particle has an action $\int L(v) dt$. Relativistically $A = -m_0 \int \sqrt{1-v^2} dt$ ($c=1$) and nonrelativistically $A = \int \frac{1}{2} m v^2 dt$. Writing $v=x/t$ and treating x and t as independent yields:

$$dA/dx \text{ partial} = p \quad ((1a)) \text{ and } dA/dt \text{ partial} = -E \quad ((1b)) \text{ or } A = -Et + px \quad ((1c))$$

Writing ((1a)) as an eigenvalue equation yields $-id/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx) \quad ((2)).$

In (1) we argued that quantum interactions are linked to momentum impulse hits and velocity is not a main consideration even though it exists and a fast moving particle probably undergoes an interaction much faster than a slowly moving one. The main point is that the result of the interaction does not depend on time or velocity, but on momentum. Thus $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$ yield the same two slit (or single slit) interference/diffraction pattern (although for a high v , the particle arrives at the detector much more quickly). Thus a free particle moves in space with a velocity v and time is present, but it carries a momentum wave $\exp(ipx)$ (no time) which tracks phase in space and is critical for describing impulse interactions.

Classically there are problems with a potential $V(x)$. Quantum mechanically one may argue that there is no smooth acceleration of a free particle. Rather it undergoes an impulse hit which changes its momentum. A potential picture would suggest probabilistic momentum hits of the form $V_k \exp(ikx)$ where V_k is a weight and a distribution of free particles: $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx)$. One may note that there are two sets of interactions in the scenario. The $\exp(ipx)$'s interact with the $V_k \exp(ikx)$ impulse hits, but they also interfere with each other.

Averaging over k

For a two slit interference problem one may ignore velocity and time and even the form of the potential (set of impulse hits) by the two slits. One simply uses $\exp(ipx)$ as a probability and considers interactions with each slit in a OR fashion. The modulus of this sum then describes the overall interference distribution.

In the case of impulse hits $V_k \exp(ikx)$ summing over k yields:

$$\text{Sum over } k \ V_k \exp(ikx) = V(x) \quad ((3))$$

Thus there is a spatially dependent function $V(x)$ which is an average involving interference, but no longer contains momentum explicitly. One may consider:

$$V(x+dx) = V(x) + dx \ dV/dx \quad ((4))$$

The second term on the RHS is: $dV/dx = \text{Sum over } k \ ik \ exp(ikx) \ V_k$ which is a kind of average using interference of impulse hits delivered as one moves from x to $x+dx$. Moving from x to $x+dx$, however, introduces direction and time into the scenario. These are classical notions. One no longer deals simply with momentum i.e. the momentum wave $\exp(ipx)$. There is also flow in the problem now i.e. velocity with momentum being considered as a "quantity" (even though it is also a flow of mass/energy). The point we wish to make is that even though momentum is flow, $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$ represents two velocities, but the same momentum. Now one has to consider average momentum together with its velocity flow. This distinguishes between m_1v_1 and m_2v_2 .

The distribution $\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ exp(ipx)$ includes both forward and backwards motion, but is also associated with an average flow in space. Just as an impulse hit deals with a mass/energy flux i.e. p , we suggest that an average momentum hit affects momentum flux i.e.

$$(\overline{p(x)} + d \overline{p(x)}) (\overline{v(x)} + d \overline{v(x)}) = 2 \overline{p(x)} \overline{v(x)} \quad ((5))$$

Given that one introduces direction into the problem and ((5)) involves both forward and backward motion (with $a(p)=a(-p)$ or $a(p)=-a(-p)$) we introduce .5. The the change in the momentum flux is:

$$\text{Change in momentum flux} = \overline{p(x)} \overline{v(x)} \quad ((6))$$

We equate this to the average momentum imparted i.e. $-dV/dx$ to obtain:

$$\overline{p(x)} (1/m) \overline{v(x)} = -dV/dx \quad \text{or} \quad d/dx \overline{p(x)} \overline{p(x)}/2m = -d/dx V \quad ((7))$$

$$\text{This leads to:} \quad \overline{p(x)} \overline{p(x)}/2m + V(x) = E \quad ((8))$$

At this point $\overline{p(x)}$ has not been defined specifically. Instead of using two separate averages we consider $\overline{p(x)} = \overline{p_{rms}(x)}$ so:

$$\langle p^2/2m \rangle + V(x) = E \quad ((8))$$

Statistically this is:

$$\{ \sum \overline{p} a(p) p^2/2m \exp(ipx) \} / W(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((9))$$

Multiplying by $W(x)$ shows a $V(x)W(x)$ interaction term added to the first term of the LHS times $W(x)$ to yield $EW(x)$. In other words these two terms combine to yield a constant time $W(x)$ the distribution of free particle momenta. This is like an equilibrium scenario i.e. the interactions ultimately leave the distribution unchanged except for the factor of E .

To see specifically at a p level what is happening in ((9)) one may write $V(x)$ as a Fourier series and collect coefficients of p i.e

$$p^2/2m a(p) + \sum \overline{k} V_k a(p-k) = E_n a(p) \quad ((10))$$

Thus one sees $V_k \exp(ikx)$ giving impulse hits to various $\exp(i(p-k)x)$ free particle waves to create $\exp(ipx)$, but at the same time there is the average momentum flux term .5 $\overline{p} \overline{v}$ as well.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that Newton's second law concerns flux because momentum is rest mass flux mv nonrelativistically. This flux, however, behaves like a quantity in impulse hits i.e. one does not need to worry about flow in time when considering $2p = \int F(t) dt$. In (1) we argued that a quantum mechanical free particle has velocity and moves through space and time. It too has a flux i.e. momentum px , but we argue that this is linked to interactions with potentials. We suggested there is a momentum wave $\exp(ipx)$ (no time) associated with the free

particle motion and this governs interactions. For example, $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$ have the same interference pattern even though each particle moves differently through space. In the case of a potential $V(x)$ in classical mechanics, we suggest that in quantum mechanics one has a set of probabilistic momentum hits given by $V_k \exp(ikx)$. K is momentum and again a flux, but is treated as a quantity. If one sums over k one obtains a x -dependent function $V(x)$. Considering $V(x+dx)-V(x)$ introduces direction and time as one moves from x to $x+dx$. Note Sum over k $V_k \exp(ikx)$ considers both k and $-k$. Thus considering motion from x to $x+dx$ seems to restore classical mechanical ideas of direction, velocity and time even though a specific impulse hit does not require these.. dV/dx is the average k imparted and we argue that it is linked to a change in momentum flux as now there is velocity in the problem.

In particular: $(p(\text{ave})(x) + dp(\text{ave})) (v(\text{ave})(x) + dv(\text{ave})) = 2 p(\text{ave})(x) dv(\text{ave})$. Quantum mechanics, however, considers p and $-p$ so we multiply by $.5$ to impose motion in one direction (for $a(p)=a(-p)$ or $a(p)=-a(-p)$). Then: $p(\text{ave}) d/dx p(\text{ave})/m = - dV/dx$ we suggest.

This leads to the notion of an average kind of kinetic energy i.e. $d/dx .5 p(\text{ave})p(\text{ave})/m = -dV/dx$ or $.5 p(\text{ave})p(\text{ave})/m + V(x) = E$. One must still define the average used. We suggest $p(\text{ave})=p_{rms}$ so one has:

$$(\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ p^2/2m \ \exp(ipx)) / W(x) + V(x) = E$$

This is also statistical in nature because multiplying by $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$ produces an interaction term $V(x)W(x)$ plus the interfering momentum flux related term (i.e. kinetic energy) yielding $EW(x)$ i.e. a constant times the original distribution. Thus there is no acceleration of a specific p , but there is a v_{rms} created which shows direction and momentum flux in space and creates a kind of average classical picture. In other words, one starts with a flux $p=mv$ (nonrelativistic). This is linked to a momentum wave $\exp(ipx)$ with no time or velocity in the picture. Considering averages of impulse hits involving momentum, however, leads to the introduction of a second flux, namely momentum flux which ultimately leads to kinetic energy and a classical looking v_{rms} equation which holds for all energy levels.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Quantum Momentum Scaling p_x and Special Relativity (preprint, zenodo, 2022)